

BALLOT BREEZE

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ABSTRACT: India is the largest democracy in the world and elections are a cornerstone of our country. Representatives are chosen from among prominent leaders to rule the country and handle public affairs, legislation, and constitutional amendments. The daunting task is to make elections fair and combat fraud by maintaining transparency in the electoral process and protecting election integrity. Free Rampage Elections are one of the most important issues in today's situation. It's like looking for a needle in a haystack that requires eyes and a lot of money being spent to make sure elections are fair and unbiased. Confidentiality is also important to ensure election integrity and prevent voter coercion, intimidation, and ballot selling. However, these days, undesirable forces are seen committing false voting, and as criticisms of election fraud have recently poured in, the results of public opinion polls and the actual evaluation of the people are becoming ambiguous. Like many other computerized voting systems, traditional polling place voting methods pose many administrative and logistical challenges in terms of cost, voter misinterpretation, and vote counting. This project proposes the design of a new state-of-the-art electronic voting machine to ensure election legitimacy in order to provide an affordable solution based on a practical biometric system utilizing facial recognition and near-field communication technologies.

Keywords: CNN(Convolution Neural Networks), Deep learning, SVM(Support Vector Machine), KNN(K-Nearest Neighbor), ABCD(Asymmetry, Border, Color, Diameter), SVM(Support Vector Machine), Dermoscopic, Pre-processing, Feature Extraction, Segmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a large democracy like India where leaders are elected by the people, elections play an important role. Elections preserve the true function of the state because they give people the opportunity to choose their personal government. Therefore, elections must be a free and fair process. Every citizen in a democratic country has the right to vote as he or she wishes. One of the fundamental problems with traditional democratic systems is that they require enormous amounts of labor and resources. Some people may also be concerned about illegal publications about movements during these types of elections or preparations. The traditional method of electoral voting used in our country has several disadvantages, including machine downtime, potential for violence, time consumption, resource consumption, and venue arrangement. Because voters have to reach polling places, many people are unable to vote. Some people, such as those who live far from their polling place or original place of birth, are allowed to vote. Therefore, to eliminate these shortcomings, a new system called an online voting system was introduced that provides accuracy, security, flexibility, and mobility. An online voting system in a web application for use in election processes. Initially, the election process used ballot paper techniques. Then, electronic voting machines that were easy to store and operate appeared. It's safer than a ballot and takes less time. Now we have proposed a biometric authentication system to make the voting process more secure and reduce the time taken for the voting process. Using this, voters can use their system to strengthen their votes for their preferred candidates. Facial recognition technology is used to verify whether a citizen is a valid consumer or not. We provide many modules that allow administrators to log into the tool and show numerous tasks. Users can also log in to exercise their voting rights. When a voter uses the system, the system uses a webcam to capture an image of the voter and attempts to match it with an image stored in a database. If the two images are identical, the voter can vote. Most higher education institutions in Kenya hold regular elections to elect faculty leadership of their own choosing. They proposed a process to create an online system that would include a system for recruiting voters, counting votes, verifying votes, and declaring results, which could be a valuable response to replace the current structure of Kenyan institutions.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. In 2020, Vivek S.K. developed a secure, transparent, and decentralized electronic voting system using the Hyperledger Sawtooth blockchain architecture [1]. Voters can cast their votes through limited access to the system through polling places, and their votes are recorded in an immutable blockchain state. There is no possibility of vote manipulation, ensuring the fairness and reliability of the election process. About the zero possibility of vote manipulation, issues of fairness and reliability of the election process were also considered. The technologies/platforms used were Angular 8, Node.js, Amazon RDS and Saw blockchain, Python with API, Docker technology, and Amazon

Web Services (AWS).

2. In 2021, Shubham Gupta, Divanshu Jain and Milind Thomas Temalil developed a system where voters are registered in the system database well before election time. Now, the first step of voting requires voters to verify their identity. Once your government ID like Aadhar card or voting card with correct photo is verified, you proceed to the second step. In the second stage, the voter must go through a facial reconstruction process. Once proper matching or verification is complete, voters proceed to the next step of voting for candidates using electronic voting machines. Voting results are publicly displayed for the satisfaction of voters. Voting data is then continuously uploaded to ThingSpeak servers. The Department of Elections' central office can track data in a more reliable way to avoid future discrepancies or changes. The technologies/platforms used were PyCharm, JetBrains IDE using Python, IoT, ThingSpeak, open source computer vision library OpenCV, and Arduino.

3. In 2016, Neelam Keith and J. V. Kutty developed a web-based voting system technology that allows voters to vote regardless of their location. The security of all information is a critical issue and is very sensitive to online voting systems. The system does not use biometric applications and performs voter authentication without using biometric features. In this system, votes are encrypted using the AES encryption algorithm to ensure security. Problem solved to save time and improve system performance. The mentioned approach is cost-effective and at the same time meets the security requirements of online voting systems. The technologies/platforms used were visual encryption and AES algorithm.

4. 2020 Nasir Abdul Karim Jaber Al-Habib, Dr. Nicolae Goga, Haider Abdullah Ali¹ and Sarmad Monadel Sabri Al-Ghayar described a mobile voting application tailored to Iraq's specific conditions in the context of COVID-19. In today's society, the applications we are talking about can also be seen as being of vital help to many countries during the COVID-19 pandemic. This application is based on mobile technology. Mobile technology was chosen because almost everyone in Iraq has a cell phone, even if people don't have computers. The technologies/platforms used were Android Studio, PHP-Restful service for backend components and MySQL database.

5. In 2020, Rupak T. M., Dr. R. Sumati has developed a scheme to provide a secure electronic voting system using the voter's biometrics and VID (Virtual Identity) obtained from the Aadhar database for voting and using digital signatures as keys. Encrypts votes within a block [5]. Integrating Aadhar into electronic voting systems will prevent duplication or forgery of votes. Blockchain technology was used as the technology/platform.

6. In 2005, Claudia Garzana-Zamora, Francisco Rodrenquez-Enriquez, and Daniel Ortiz-Arroyo developed SELES (Secure Electronic-Voting System for Medium-Scale Online Elections).

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Creating and proposing a smart voting system with enhanced security than the existing one uses image processing and CNN for face and fingerprint recognition. The basic level of security is achieved when the voter's face and fingerprints are recognized by a system using the Electoral Commission's current facial image and fingerprint database. If the resulting image matches the voter's image in the database, the voter can vote in the election. The Haar cascade algorithm is used to recognize the face part of the image and extract features. The web platform and algorithms were developed using Visual Studio and HTML technologies. small parts. The matching method compares the fingerprint image with the image provided by the National Election Commission. If the captured images match, the voter can vote.

HAAR CASCADE ALGORITHM

Face detection is an object detection algorithm used to identify objects in images or videos. The algorithm was trained to recognize faces using Haar features, which are a set of square shape functions. We then use a classifier to detect non-faces (1). (0). Face recognition occurs in four steps. The first step is Haar feature detection using integrated images, the third step is Adaboost, and the fourth step is a series of classifiers..

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK (CNN)

1. A convolutional neural network (CNN) is a type of deep learning algorithm that is particularly suitable for recognition and image processing tasks. It consists of several layers including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. CNN architecture is based on the visual processing of the human brain and is well suited to capturing hierarchical structures and spatial dependencies within images.

The main components of a convolutional neural network are:

- 1.Convolutional layer.** These layers apply convolution operations to the input image using filters (also called kernels) to detect features such as edges, textures, and more complex patterns. Convolution operations help maintain spatial relationships between pixels.
- 2.Full layer.** Pooling layers reduce the spatial dimension of the input data, reducing computational complexity and the number of parameters in the network. Max pooling is a common pooling operation that selects the maximum value from a group of adjacent pixels.
- 3.Activation function.** Nonlinear activation functions, such as Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), introduce nonlinearity into your model, allowing you to explore more complex relationships in your data.
- 4. Fully connected layers.** These layers are responsible for making predictions based on high-level features obtained from previous layers. They connect every neuron in one layer to every neuron in the next layer.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Since the proposed concept is a completely web-based system, the main relevant features are web technologies such as database creation and image processing properties, which define the software requirements of the system. This is an approved government site. Voters can use this website to vote. Eligible voters can enter through facial and fingerprint recognition. The site opens for voters on Election Day. The server stores fingerprints and facial images received from the National Election Commission. Voters can open the website by entering their IP address. When you open the website and click the vote button, the voter's face and fingerprints are captured through any device using the website, including laptops, PCs, and mobile cameras. Captured images are received from the server. The server looks through all the images in the database and tries to find a matching image among the registered images. Once the face and fingerprints are confirmed to match, the voter is registered and recognized by the National Election Commission and can vote. Face detection is performed using the Haar Cascade algorithm. If there is no match, the page will display a message saying the voter is not recognized and cannot vote. If the fingerprint image matches, the fingerprint image is stored on the server. Take 10 fingerprints and calculate the positions of 10 fingers. By comparing the two images, the correct fingerprint of the voter can be verified. Fingerprint image matching is accomplished by using CNN to compare input data with images stored in the database. The image is accompanied by an ID number and a voting page where voters can vote for their preferred party from a list of options displayed. Once you click on your preferred group, you will not be able to change your selection and the remaining options will also be disabled. The server accepts the votes of authenticated voters and stores them. The number of votes for each party candidate is also maintained. This makes even counting votes very simple, and missions, candidates or voters do not have to wait days to know the results.

Step 1: Image Acquisition

Image acquisition is the process of capturing an image from an input source. Captured images are saved in a separate folder called Test Folder. The data sets in this folder are called test data sets.

Step 2: Image preprocessing.

This is a technique used to improve image quality and remove noise from images. The captured images are processed before being implemented in other stages.

Step 3: Image Segmentation

Image segmentation is used to convert a digital image into multiple parts with the same identifier. It is used to identify various parts of the face and identify the boundaries of the image. In the proposed system, the segmentation step consists of image cropping, masking, and contouring.

Step 4: Feature extraction

Features are just information extracted from an image. This is a real-valued vector number that describes the image from a high-level perspective.

Step 5: Real-time detection Continuous monitoring: Online voting systems are equipped with real-time monitoring capabilities that recognize voters' faces, system performance, and network activity during elections. This monitoring process helps identify any anomalies or suspicious activity that could jeopardize the integrity of the election.

Fraud detection algorithm. We use advanced fraud detection algorithms to analyze voting patterns, detect irregularities, and identify potential instances of fraud or manipulation in real time. These algorithms can detect unusual voting behavior, such as multiple votes from the same IP address or suspicious voting patterns, and trigger alerts for further investigation.

Identity Verification: Real-time detection systems use a variety of authentication methods, including facial authentication and two-factor authentication, to verify the voter's identity in real-time. This helps prevent unauthorized access to the voting system and ensures that only eligible voters can vote.

Fig.1: Structure of algorithm

Fig.2 Face Detection

To recognize objects in images or videos, algorithms such as face detection are used, as shown in Figure 1. 1, object detection. The face detection method is learned using Haar features, which are a set of square-shaped features. Next, we use a classifier to determine whether a face is present or not. Face recognition occurs in four steps. The first step included Haar feature identification using integrated images, Adaboost (the third step and a series of classifiers).

Ten Print Image Pre-Processing

A fingerprint image can be used in this method if the two fingerprint images are identical. Ten fingerprints are captured and the properties for each fingerprint image in the repository are recorded. In this section we will consider these properties in turn, leaving the topic of auxiliary properties for the next section. When two people's fingerprints are identical and their record value is the same. A collection of 10-minute documents depicting each graphic item of the seal and its corresponding finger position was physically entered into the database. The fingerprints of both voters were identical and minute details were also recorded. Among these features are the friction points on the fingers. It is called the end of the ridge. The ideal features of the first of 10 image prints were identified by the automated AFIS system.

A. Detecting Haar features

Before the advent of the Haar function, face identification in images was performed by summing the pixel intensities of each image. This required a lot of hard work and effort. In contrast, the Haar wavelet, which identifies faces by simultaneously considering a smaller subset of faces, computes the sum of the intensity of each pixel and then compares the two sums. Grayscale was adjusted for pixels in a black-and-white image.

Fig.3: Pixel intensities of detected Haar Features (a) ideal case (b) real case

Detecting Haar feature in the image

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{dark}^n I(x) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{white}^n I(x) \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Ideal case: $\Delta = (1/8)*(8) - (1/8)*0 = 1$

Real case: $\Delta = (1/8)*(5.9) - (1/8)*(1.3) = 0.575$

The Haar function recognizes rectangular features very well, making it a very useful method for face detection. The eyes can be seen in the picture. 3(b) above. The part of the face corresponding to the cheeks is lighter and the darker part is the eyes. The eyes are usually the first to be noticed because they are the darkest part of the face compared to the rest of the face, regardless of whether they are shades of grey. Another illustration is shown in Figure 3(a), where the bridge of the nose is darker and often higher than the buccal part of the face. The Haar trait, which is good at recognizing lines and edges, is initially how we identify faces or specific parts of them. Some Haar features are shown in Figure 4(a), (b), (c) above.

Fig. 4: Some common Haar features (a) Nose (b) Eyes (c) Mouth

B. Integral images

The above calculation returns a huge number of functions. The integrated image is used to determine which features need to be considered. This is a special algorithm designed to find the sum of values in a rectangular subset of a grid. The sum of the pixel intensities of the window. When selecting a particular window, this algorithm calculates the cumulative sum of pixel intensities across rows and columns, minimizing the number of operations required to determine whether a window is useful. Area of the face that needs to be detected. For the table on the left, if we consider the field below as a subset of faces where the numbers represent the intensity of the pixels, as shown in Figure 5, it should be 1 5 2 4. 5 (a), (b))

Fig.5: The generated subset of a grid

(a) input image (b) integral image

C. Adaboost

Not only can it have a lot of features, it can also be meaningless. It's a feature built into the face. Adaboost trains a classifier using both the strongest and weakest features. The algorithm produces a “weak” classifier and a “strong” classifier. In this context, a “weak” classifier is defined as one with an error rate of less than 50%, indicating that the feature is most likely to belong to the face region. On the other hand, strong classifiers have low error rates and are clearly part of the face. As a result, these weak classifiers are combined using Adaboost to create a single strong classifier capable of face detection.

D. Cascade of classifiers

The image contains areas with faces and areas without faces. Characteristics found in subsections and introduced at various stages of classification. No other features are considered. Once the process passes the first stage, the second set of features is applied. Each scene's window is an essential front area. Cascade saves time, effort, and energy at every step of the process. Windows only recognizes facial features. The steps are combined to form one large window that generates the faces to be detected, but the classifier cascade has no place in the face region.

RESULTS

Any democracy must have elections as its cornerstone because it is only possible for the people to choose their own government. However, the current election process our nation is riddled with flaws and gaps that the candidates and political parties take advantage of. Numerous flaws in the current system, such as the potential for duplicate votes, the ability to rig electronic voting machines, and the ability to falsify the count, distort what democracy really means. Most places use electronic voting machines, which require a lot of time and energy and should only be used in designated locations. The machine is costly and requires additional manpower for monitoring and transportation. All of the aforementioned issues are addressed by the system that is being suggested here. Through the fingerprint and face recognition smart voting system acknowledgment, those who don't live in the same area, the elderly, or those who find it difficult to stand in line for extended periods of time will all gain. Voters can conveniently cast their ballots from any location, and this also lessens the likelihood of multiple votes being cast. This online voting system employs the Haar Cascade Algorithm in image processing to identify voters' faces. to accurately capture the eyes, mouth, and whole face and compare it to a database image of a face. CNN Deep Learning is used to calculate the matching of fingerprint images. CNN processed the large-scale image in less time thanks to its computational efficiency. An ANN takes a long time to train. CNN operates in two stages: image classification and feature detection. Face and features of the fingerprint image are extracted and compared to the database. when they line up. Voting will be permitted by the voter. Any leader may be chosen by the electorate. Following that, the other leader slots are disabled. At the conclusion of the election, the votes are counted and stored on the server. Commission from servers and Clint is crucial to the system. The IP address is obtained from the official election website. When compared to the current system, the counting is extremely simple and takes very little time. following the critical data that was input into the system to separate legitimate voters from fraudulent ones. Crucially, the system created is fully web-based. Which is extremely affordable in comparison to the current systems, and very little labor will be needed if the website has robust cybersecurity. The current framework is a genuine model as well.

Accuracy: A well-designed website that is implemented with robust security measures to prevent fraud and ensure the accuracy of votes, the result could reflect the true preferences of the voters.

Accessibility: This online voting website can increase accessibility to the voting process, potentially leading to higher voter turnout and more representative results.

Efficiency: Online voting can streamline the voting process, reducing the time and resources required for traditional methods like paper ballots. This could lead to quicker dissemination of results.

Secure: A safe user experience with two levels of security.

User Experience: The usability and user-friendliness of the website can affect voter participation and satisfaction. A well-designed website with intuitive interfaces can encourage more people to vote and enhance confidence in the results. A better user interface can increase the voter turnout.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Ensuring the integrity of elections is paramount to the functioning of a healthy democracy. This involves eradicating non-legitimate votes, thereby upholding the sanctity of the electoral process. By implementing a fair electoral system, we can guarantee that every vote counts and that the voice of the people is accurately represented. Such measures not only assure the smooth functioning of democracy but also foster trust in the electoral process. Moreover, supporting an eco-friendly environment is essential in preserving the very foundation upon which democracy thrives, ensuring that future generations inherit a sustainable world where their voices can be heard.

Developing a mobile app to facilitate voting offers a convenient and accessible option for citizens to participate in the democratic process. By leveraging secure servers, we can ensure that sensitive voter data remains protected from unauthorized access. Implementing blockchain technology further enhances security measures, as it provides a decentralized and tamper-resistant platform for storing and managing voting records. This prevents malicious users from manipulating or tampering with the data, ensuring the integrity of the voting process. Overall, by combining the convenience of mobile technology with robust security measures such as secure servers and blockchain, we can create a reliable and trustworthy platform for citizens to exercise their democratic right to vote.

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